

Community Development Strategy in the Economic Sector for Non-Profit Organization in Simpang Village (Case Study: Pasanggrahan Baranangsiang)

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ABSTRACT

This research focuses on the community development strategy in the economic sector for a non-profit organization in Simpang Village, Indonesia, with a case study of Pasanggrahan Baranangsiang. The study aims to provide an understanding of the social dynamics within Simpang Village, shedding light on the intricacies of its socio-economic condition. It delves into the challenges confronting the residents and identifies key areas that require attention and intervention for the betterment of the community. The paper also emphasizes the need for further research to explore effective collaboration models between the public sector, private sector, and non-profit organizations in the context of community development. The findings of this study are anticipated to contribute valuable insights to the formulation of informed policies and development programs that align with the real needs and aspirations of the Simpang Village community

INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, villages play an important role in national development. The lives of most of the Indonesian population are closely related to activities in the village, especially in the agricultural sector which is the main source of livelihood (Khotimah et al, 2019). The important role of villages in national development is also related to the large potential of natural resources they have, such as agricultural land and other natural wealth. In addition, villages have an important role in national food security, with the majority of food production coming from villages. Economic development in villages can create more equal income and reduce disparities between regions (Mukaramah et al, 2011). Rural development can also reduce the pressure of uncontrolled rural-urban migration. The migration of people from villages to cities often has a number of negative impacts, both on the people who migrate, their villages of origin, and the cities where they move (Mlambo, 2018). Therefore, strengthening and developing villages should be a strategic focus in Indonesia's national development efforts.

Village development must involve the active role of various parties, including the government, local communities, the private sector, academics and the media. By involving the initiatives of all parties, village development can become more holistic and sustainable (Pugra et al, 2021). In addition, the active involvement of non-profit organizations (NPOs) is equally crucial for the holistic and sustainable development of villages. NPOs tackle a vast spectrum of social issues, offering solutions and achieving progress in areas that public administrations cannot or do not cover effectively. (Ciucescu, 2009). Sustainable development requires long-term commitment and collaboration. By including various stakeholders, village development projects are more likely to have enduring impacts.

In 2003, a non-profit organization called Pasanggrahan Baranangsiang (PBS) was formed in Simpang Village, Garut, Indonesia to serve the community and improve the standard of living of the people. Initially, this organization was active in the education sector by establishing an Open School for junior high school level. However, as time went by, the organization realized that there were many problems that occurred in the community, especially in the economic sector such as poverty and unemployment. People need solutions that can help them increase their income. According to the village head, as many as 782 out of 1,351 families or around 58% of the total families, are classified as poor families. The migration of villagers to cities or other areas is also increasingly common. Urban areas offer more job opportunities, career prospects, higher wages, better social conditions, making them attractive and appear more stable for individuals and families. This then encourages population migration from villages to cities (Liao & Yip, 2018).

The objective of this research is to map the social landscape of Simpang Village, explore the challenges faced by its residents, and unveil opportunities for community development in the economic sector. This study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the social dynamics within Simpang Village, shedding light on the intricacies of its socio-economic condition. By delving into the challenges confronting the residents, the research aims to identify key areas

that require attention and intervention for the betterment of the community. The findings of this study are anticipated to contribute valuable insights to the formulation of informed policies and development programs that align with the real needs and aspirations of the Simpang Village community. Through this research, an effort is made to bridge the gap between theoretical understanding and practical implementation, paving the way for a more holistic approach to community development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Definition of Community

A community can be described as a group of people who share common interests and values (Rein, 1997). It is a social entity organized around shared values, demonstrating social cohesion within a specific geographical location. The concept of community is broad and encompasses groups of people interacting in a common area, extending to a national or global scale. The core of community lies in individuals' perception of interconnectedness, interdependence, shared responsibilities, and common goals. Communities are characterized by shared traits and the identification of members with common judgments, moral standards, and cultural orientations. In the context of a village community, it refers to a group residing in a small, rural area with similar social, economic, and cultural traits (Orbawati et al, 2020). Villages are societies where residents primarily rely on agriculture, fishing, livestock, or a combination thereof for their livelihoods. The social and cultural frameworks of village communities revolve around sustaining these livelihoods, with kinship playing a significant role in the organization of village life.

Community Development

Community development is the process of building capacities (social, intellectual, physical, financial, and political) aimed at improving the quality of life in low to middle-income environments (Ferguson & Dickens, 2000). It goes beyond mere infrastructure development, involving collective concern for social issues, encouraging active participation of marginalized groups, forming partnerships with the public sector, and adopting collaborative principles in organization (Frisby & Millar, 2002). In other words, community development is not just about providing resources but also about creating an environment that enables individuals and groups to support and collaborate with each other for common well-being. Kristina et al. (2020) highlight key success factors for community development efforts. These include a supportive community environment, measurable project management outcomes, community project management involvement, guidance and support from government, extensive community participation, mentoring of community leadership, and instilling a spirit of perseverance, self-reliance, and cooperation in the community. In other words, community development is a journey together, not a top-down project. It is rooted in citizen empowerment, collaboration cultivation, and collective commitment to building a better future. Infrastructure is just a tool, while its core strength lies in the web of brotherhood, active participation, and the spirit of mutual aid that is woven within the community.

Community Needs

Community needs encompass the requirements, wants, and aspirations of a community that are essential for enhancing the well-being of its residents. These needs are discerned through a community needs assessment, a methodical process that involves gathering information about the community's strengths, weaknesses, and available resources (Carter et al., 1992). They span a diverse array of dimensions, including social, economic, health, educational, and environmental factors. The identification and subsequent addressing of community needs represent a pivotal undertaking in elevating the overall quality of life within a community. Crucially, involving community members in the identification and prioritization of these needs is imperative. As residents are intimately familiar with their specific challenges, their active participation ensures the incorporation of valuable insights into potential solutions. Once community needs are identified, collaboration among stakeholders becomes paramount. This includes engagement from government agencies, non-profit organizations, and community groups, working collectively to devise and implement strategies and programs aimed at addressing these needs and fostering an enhanced state of well-being within the community. The collaborative effort to recognize, prioritize, and respond to community needs is instrumental in creating sustainable improvements and promoting the prosperity of the community as a whole.

Stakeholders

A group of individuals or groups who have a direct or indirect interest in the outcome of a social decision are called a community or social policy stakeholders (Suharto, 2012). Stakeholder analysis serves as a strategic management tool employed by organizations to systematically identify and comprehend the diverse individuals, groups, or entities – commonly referred to as stakeholders – whose interests may be influenced by or hold significance for the organization's activities (Keremidchiev, 2021). The foundational concept supporting stakeholder analysis is rooted in stakeholder theory, a framework pioneered and popularized by R. Edward Freeman during the 1980s. Central to stakeholder theory is the argument that organizational accountability extends beyond shareholders to encompass a broader spectrum of stakeholders, including employees, customers or beneficiaries, suppliers, communities, and others. According to this theory, organizations are obligated to consider the interests and needs of all these stakeholders in their decision-making processes. In essence, stakeholder analysis and the underlying stakeholder theory underscore the importance of a holistic approach to organizational management, acknowledging and integrating the perspectives and concerns of a diverse array of stakeholders for more informed and inclusive decision-making.

Social Mapping

Social mapping, as described by Handoyo (2016), serves as a tool for comprehending the social landscape of a community, uncovering its potentials, and devising models for community empowerment. This approach proves invaluable in collecting comprehensive data about a village, encompassing the distribution and spatial arrangement of castes, ethnic groups, social institutions, and economic elements. Social mapping offers insights into the intricate fabric of

family structures, interpersonal patterns, and relationships, as well as the presence of governmental institutions and the educational background of residents. Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA), with social mapping as a prominent component, stands out as one of the most widely used methods in this context. It represents an authentic approach to understanding the social reality experienced by local residents, delving into aspects such as social stratification, demographics, settlement patterns, and social infrastructure. A key feature of this method is its emphasis on the active involvement of various societal levels, fostering creativity in how information about their social environment is presented. Ultimately, the information derived from social mapping becomes a crucial resource for comprehending the social conditions prevalent in local communities. This knowledge, in turn, forms a solid foundation for development planning that is not only more attuned to the specific needs and realities of the community but is also inclusive and participatory in nature. Social mapping thus stands as a valuable tool in the arsenal of community development, providing a nuanced understanding of the social dynamics that underpin effective and contextually relevant planning and empowerment initiatives.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses social mapping to discern macroeconomic factors in Simpang Village. Social mapping involves the systematic collection and analysis of data concerning various social aspects of a community. The gathered information encompasses demographic, economic, socio-cultural, and ecological dimensions. The purpose of this data collection is to gain insights into the social conditions of the community, identify prevalent social issues, and formulate strategies to address these challenges. Social mapping incorporates diverse techniques, and beyond just techniques, the methods and concepts employed often vary (Gunawan & Sutrisno, 2021). The chosen approach for this research is participatory, involving observations, in-depth interviews, and active participation in community activities. This participatory method facilitates a more profound understanding of the society under study and the challenges it confronts.

RESULT

Simpang Village Geographic Information

Simpang Village is part of the Cibalong District, consisting of 11 villages. The population of this village totals 4,179 residents and is organized into four hamlets: Sindangsari, Dahu, Bojongsirna, and Petakan,

Figure 1. Simpang Village Map

The delineation of administrative boundaries for Simpang Village is outlined as follows:

- South: Najaten Village, Cibalong District
- North: Toblong Village, Peundeuy District
- West: Maroko Village, Cibalong District
- East: Campakasari Village, Bojong Gambir District

Simpang Village is situated at a distance of 37 km from the district capital, 84 km from the regency capital, and 200 km from the provincial capital. The considerable distances contribute to the relatively poor accessibility of Simpang Village. The travel time to the regency capital is around 240 minutes, to the district capital is 90 minutes, and to the provincial capital takes about 4 hours. Moreover, the village faces challenges related to limited availability of public transportation. Only a few public transportation options operate, and their schedules are irregular.

Simpang Village Landscape

Covering an expanse of 2,014 hectares, Simpang Village comprises various land uses, including 422 hectares of dry land utilized for fields, settlements, and yards, 88 hectares dedicated to rice fields, 408 hectares allocated for plantations, 10 hectares designated for public facilities, and the remaining portion is characterized as forested land. In its entirety, Simpang Village functions as a seasonal plantation area, positioned at an elevation ranging from 250 to 300 meters above sea level, and maintains an average temperature of approximately 28 °C. Situated in a lowland region with hilly topography, the village faces challenges in road infrastructure. The roads' poor quality is particularly evident due to the complex terrain, making the construction and maintenance of asphalt

roads challenging. Consequently, the asphalt roads frequently incur damage, posing potential hazards to road users.

Figure 2. Hilly Topography

In Simpang Village, residents have access to clean water through four primary sources: rivers, rainwater, wells, and water springs. However, due to concerns about the cleanliness of river water and rainwater, the inhabitants predominantly depend on water sourced from wells and springs for drinking and consumption. Notably, during the dry season, there is a noticeable inadequacy of water for agricultural and plantation activities, posing challenges to meet the needs of these sectors.

Figure 3. Water Springs

Based on soil types and fertility, Simpang Village predominantly features soils with red, yellow, black, and gray hues. The soil textures vary, including loam, sandy, and dusty compositions. Overall, the soil fertility levels are relatively modest, with only a limited portion categorized as highly fertile. This reduced fertility is attributed to the presence of abundant mining materials within the soil. Simpang Village is home to various types of mining materials, including coal and gold. However, these materials are characterized as young rocks, rendering them economically unviable for extraction and utilization.

Figure 4. Soil Conditions

The Table 1 illustrates the trends and changes in commodities or resources within Simpang Village:

Table 1. Commodity Trends and Changes

Commodity Trends And Changes			
Commodity	1990 - 1999	2000 - 2010	2011 - 2021
CROPS			
Coconut	v v v	v v v	v v
Clove	v v v	v v	v
Banana	v v v v	v v v v	v v v
Rice plant	v v v	v v v	v v
Horticulture	v v v v	v v v	v v
Vanilla	v	v v	v v
Clove	v v v	v v	v
Nutmeg	0	0	v
Palm sugar	v v v v	v v v	v v v
Cardamom	0	v	v v v v
WOODY/ANNUAL PLANTS			
Fruits	v	v v	v v v
Albasia	v v v v	v v v v	v v
Mahogany	v v v v	v	v
Teak	v v v v	v v	v
Rubber	v v v	v v v	v v
FARM			
Laying Hens	0	0	v
Broiler	v	v v	v v

Kampong chicken	vvv	v	v
Goat	vvv	v	v
Sheep	vv	vv	vv
Cow	vvv	v	v
Bee	0	0	v
FISHERY			
Nile Tilapia	vvv	vvv	vv
Catfish	vvv	vvv	vv
Goldfish	vvv	vvv	vv
INDUSTRY			
Home industry	v	v	v
MINING			
Gold Mining Company	v	0	0
Public	vv	v	0
OTHER			
Worship Building	v	vv	vvv
Rice field area	vvv	vv	vv
Middle school building	0	v	vv
High School Building	0	0	v
Residential building	v	vv	vvv
Plantation land area	vvvv	vvv	vvv
Community Health Center	v	v	v
Market (once a week)	0	v	v

Note:

- 0 = None
- v = Very little
- vv = Little
- vvv = Many

Simpang Village Demographic Information

Simpang Village is home to a population of 4,179 individuals, comprising 2,162 male residents and 2,017 female residents. The village has a total of 1,351 households, with 138 of them headed by women. Among these households, approximately 58% or 782 families are categorized as poor.

Analyzing the population structure based on age, the majority of Simpang Village residents fall within the productive age range. Following the guidelines set by the Indonesian government, individuals considered part of the workforce are those aged 15 to 65 years. Consequently, Simpang Village boasts a workforce of approximately 2,800 people.

Figure 5. Population Pyramid

With the enhancement of road and transportation accessibility in Simpang Village, a noticeable trend emerges - an increase in the number of individuals migrating from rural to urban areas. This phenomenon, commonly referred to as rural-urban migration or urbanization, is predominantly propelled by economic factors. While the precise count of Simpang Village residents engaged in rural-urban migration is not accurately determined, information gleaned from the 2022 village head election suggests that approximately 1,000 eligible voters were residing outside the village. Despite their physical location elsewhere, these individuals are still administratively included in the population of Simpang Village. So, it is estimated that the number of Simpang Village residents who have undergone rural-urban migration likely exceeds 1,000 people.

Simpang Village Economic Information

The economic landscape of Simpang Village is shaped by a diverse range of factors, incorporating both natural and socio-cultural elements. The challenging hilly topography and soil conditions in the village make it impractical to rely solely on agriculture or plantations for income generation. Consequently, community members seek alternative livelihoods beyond these sectors. Many residents migrate to urban areas in pursuit of higher incomes, aspiring to secure roles as factory workers; however, due to intense competition, they often opt for alternative occupations such as household assistants and street vendors.

Meanwhile, those who choose to remain in the village actively explore diverse job opportunities to augment their income. The reliance on a single income source is uncommon, with most individuals engaging in supplementary employment. Consequently, categorizing the population by occupation proves challenging, given the dynamic nature of community members' work preferences.

According to village government data, Simpang Village hosts a household and small/medium-sized industry sector, engaging in the production of various commodities such as palm sugar, bamboo, tempeh, handicrafts, furniture, and snacks like chips and crackers. This sector serves as a source of employment for approximately 600 individuals. The trade sector within the village includes 83 kiosk owners, 146 warung owners, 14 shop owners, and 74 market traders. There are 167 individuals employed as civil servants, village officials, military personnel, and private employees. Additionally, skilled services in the village involve carpenters, masons and builders, barbers, tailors, and beauty salons, providing employment for 125 workers. The agriculture/plantation sector comprises land/garden owners, tenant farmers, and farm laborers, with a capacity to employ up to 1,485 workers.

Figure 6. Cardamom Farmers

Simpang Village Sociocultural Information

In Simpang Village, a significant majority of the population possesses educational qualifications at the elementary school and junior high school levels, as highlighted in Table 2. An interview with a junior high school teacher from Simpang Village revealed that students entering his classroom often face challenges in reading and counting.

Table 2. Education Level

Education	Male	Female
S1 graduates	12	7
D3 graduates	2	3
D2 graduates	3	2
D1 graduates	7	5
High school graduates	165	73
Junior high school graduates	238	232
Elementary school graduates	448	233
18-56 years old that not finished high school	435	245
18-56 years old that not finished junior high school	677	354
18-56 years old, not finished elementary school	0	0
18-56 years old that never attended school	0	0
7-18 years old that currently attending school	577	156
7-18 years old that never attended school	0	0
3-6 years old that in preschool	85	86
3-6 years old that have not attending preschool	57	77
Total	2706	1473

Despite facing challenges in reading and counting, individuals in Simpang Village exhibit a high level of reliability in roles that demand physical skills. This includes proficiency in crafting handicrafts, stonemasonry, welding, driving vehicles, engaging in factory work, and contributing as farm laborers or plantation workers. Their robust physical endurance is a notable characteristic, enabling them to perform tasks requiring strength and stamina effectively. Furthermore, these individuals demonstrate an ability to produce meticulous and high-quality handmade products within a relatively short timeframe.

Figure 7. Student's Wood Craft Results

The residents of Simpang Village have access to modern technologies such as smartphones and computers, although not everyone in the community possesses these devices. The adoption of the internet has been on the rise, particularly following the pandemic that prompted a shift towards online learning. However, challenges persist as the internet connection remains unstable, and not all operator networks deliver good quality service within the village. Notably, the absence of courier services reaching the village has deterred the establishment of online businesses in this community.

Simpang Village Ecological Information

The degradation of the environment in Simpang Village has become increasingly apparent over the last 5-10 years. In the recent dry season, the community in experienced water shortages due to rivers drying up and reduced water absorption. This environmental challenge is exacerbated by a lack of knowledge and awareness regarding sustainable natural resource management practices. Frequently, community members resort to convenient yet environmentally harmful methods, including the application of chemical fertilizers and field burning. These practices contribute to environmental degradation and underscore the importance of promoting sustainable approaches to resource management in the community.

The removal of forest vegetation not only endangers the existence of diverse plant and animal species but also leads to the loss of crucial soil layers. This, in turn, elevates the risk of landslides and soil erosion, posing a significant threat to the surrounding environment. Urgent attention and proactive measures are needed to address these environmental challenges and promote sustainable practices in Simpang Village.

Figure 8. Landslide

Stakeholder Analysis

Stakeholder analysis is a crucial process undertaken by Pasanggrahan Barangsiang to identify, evaluate, and comprehend the individuals or groups that can influence or be influenced by the success or failure of their community development project or initiative. This analysis not only recognizes stakeholders with whom the organization has already established successful engagement but also aims to identify entities that should be considered stakeholders but have not yet been reached out yet. Stakeholders who have been successfully engaged in the initiative encompass the government, donors, academic institutions, local communities, and organization members. However, there are additional

potential stakeholders who have not yet been involved, including the private sector, other organizations, other institutions, media, and the general public. Expanding engagement to include these stakeholders could enhance the overall impact and success of the initiative by incorporating diverse perspectives, expertise, and resources.

Table 3. Pasanggrahan Baranangsiang Stakeholder Identification

Pasanggrahan Baranangsiang Stakeholder Identification	
Stakeholder	Description
Government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Village Government: Holds direct responsibility for the administration and advancement of Simpang Village • Subdistrict Government: Plays a supportive role in aiding village governments with community development and the provision of essential services.
Donors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individuals, organizations, or institutions providing funds or other resources for the organization.
Private Sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Companies: Corporate entities with CSR obligations may explore collaboration opportunities, offering financial, human resource, or in-kind support to NGOs. • Can engage in partnership with the organization to foster community economic development through business collaboration or facilitating market access for local products.
Academic Institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Universities/Colleges: Universities in Indonesia have a community service obligation, presenting an opportunity for collaboration with the organization.
Organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NGOs: Other NGOs focusing on education and environmental conservation can collaborate with Pasanggrahan Baranangsiang, ensuring synergy in community development efforts and facilitating the exchange of resources and experience.
Local Community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Beneficiaries: Individuals or groups set to directly benefit from the community development activities conducted by the organization. • Residents: The residents of Simpang Village that are affected by any changes or developments in the village. • Village leaders: The village head and other influential leaders, particularly in Simpang Village, possessing the ability to garner community support for the organization's initiatives.
Members of organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Committee of organization: Responsible for strategic decision-making, oversight, and ensuring alignment with the organization's objectives. • Staffs: Individuals managing the organization and directly engaging with the community. • Volunteers: Individuals eager to contribute to society and derive personal satisfaction from volunteer endeavors.

Media and General public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disseminating information about community development activities to the broader community can fortify the organization's presence and brand, thereby attracting increased collaboration opportunities from various parties.
Other Institution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial Institutions may collaborate with the organization to provide loans to the community, facilitating the establishment villager's businesses.

Table 4. Opportunities and Challenges the Stakeholders Present to the Organization

Challenges and Opportunities the Stakeholders Present to Organization				
Stakeholder	Opportunities	Challenges	Cooperation Level	Threat Level
Government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support and provision of funding, resources, and expertise for community development. Collaboration in advocating and implementing policies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adherence to stringent regulatory requirements. Potential hindrances from slow and intricate bureaucratic processes, impacting program timelines. Changes in political leadership may affect laws/legal. 	High	Low
Donors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial support. Networking opportunities and access to a wider donor community. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meeting specific reporting and accountability standards. Juggling multiple donor expectations and aligning project proposals with their priorities. 	High	Low
Private sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution of expertise and resources to community development projects. Establishment of partnerships based on shared values and mutual benefit. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Navigating potential conflicts of interest and ensuring clear communication and understanding between involved parties. Took a long time in negotiation process. 	High	High

<p>Academic Institutions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exchange of expertise, research, and knowledge-sharing opportunities. • Utilization of academic resources for community development. • Joint projects that align with both organizational and community needs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Balancing academic priorities with practical community needs. • Managing potential discrepancies in timelines for research projects. 	<p>High</p>	<p>Low</p>
<p>Organization</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mutual sharing of resources and information. • Potential for cultivating enduring partnerships based on shared objectives. • Collaboration on extensive initiatives for greater impact. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addressing the potential for competition in getting donors. • Ensuring coordination to prevent duplication of efforts. 	<p>High</p>	<p>High</p>
<p>Local Community</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct involvement of beneficiaries in impactful programs. • Enhancement of community capacity and welfare, along with environmental considerations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overcoming challenges related to community awareness and participation. • Responding to diverse community needs and expectations. • Managing potential resistance to change or unfamiliar initiatives. 	<p>High</p>	<p>High</p>
<p>Members of organization</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribution to the success of community development initiatives. • Personal satisfaction from engaging in meaningful activities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring consistent commitment from members of organization. • Addressing difficulties in recruiting members who match the desired qualities and capabilities. 	<p>High</p>	<p>Low</p>

Media and General public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive public relations and increased visibility. • Heightened public awareness and support, creating potential for attracting additional donors and partners. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Balancing the need for transparency with privacy concerns. • Navigating media biases and misinformation. 	Low	Low
Other Institution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborative projects for mutual benefit. • Access to additional resources and expertise. • Possibility of forging lasting partnerships based on shared goals. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aligning organizational goals and priorities. • Managing potential conflicts of interest within the organization. • Ensuring clear communication and understanding. 	High	Low

DISCUSSION

Based from the condition of Simpang Village, there are several programs that Pasanggarahan Baranangsiang can do as a non-profit organization to carry out community development in the economic sector:

Table 5. Potential Program for Community Development

Program	Reason
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical training program for farmers, emphasizing modern and efficient agricultural techniques. • Provision of assistance and access to advanced agricultural equipment to enhance productivity. • Introduction of an extension program promoting organic and sustainable farming practices. • Technical support to implement environmentally friendly agricultural methods. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance the farmers skills and knowledge will lead to increasing productivity and improving agricultural practices. • Access to better agricultural equipment can significantly improve the efficiency and productivity of farming activities. • Sustainable farming practices helps to reduce the use of harmful chemicals, preserve natural resources, and protect the environment. • Providing technical support for environmentally friendly agricultural methods ensures that farmers have the necessary guidance and expertise to implement sustainable practices effectively.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training sessions on the processing of agricultural products. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Processing agricultural products can lead to increased income for farmers, create opportunities

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of cooperatives to enhance business competitiveness. • Encourage business diversification across various sectors. • Assistance in marketing local products for broader market access, especially targeting export opportunities. 	<p>for value-added products, and the development of a more diverse and resilient local economy.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By developing cooperative, the community can pool resources, share knowledge and expertise, and collectively market their products. • By encouraging diversification, the community can reduce dependence on a single sector and explore new opportunities in different industries. This can lead to increased employment, income generation, and overall economic growth. • Marketing local products is crucial for accessing wider markets and increasing income opportunities.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entrepreneurship training for individuals interested in establishing small or medium-sized businesses. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By providing aspiring entrepreneurs with the necessary skills and knowledge, the village can encourage the establishment of new businesses, leading to increased economic activity and job creation.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving accessibility to both formal and non-formal education, coupled with enhancements to the quality of education. • Establishment of classes focusing on reading, writing, and mathematics. • Implementation of additional skills training programs through non-formal classes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The villagers in Simpang Village have low education levels. Lack of education leads to poverty and limited job opportunities in the community. People with low educational levels have a smaller chance of getting a good job and having a high income. By providing equivalent education programs, additional skills training, and non-formal classes, the villagers will have the opportunity to acquire new skills and improve their chances of finding better job opportunities. • Introducing skills training through non-formal classes will help diversify skills of the villagers. This diversification is essential for the community to adapt to emerging industrial sectors and increase innovation in local businesses. It will also open up new economic opportunities and strengthen the economic resilience of the community.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creativity training programs aimed at fostering innovation in local businesses. • Soft skills training encompassing leadership, communication, problem-solving, and collaboration. • Training programs tailored to skills required in emerging industrial sectors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By conducting a creativity training program, local businesses in Simpang Village can learn new techniques and approaches to problem-solving, which can lead to innovative ideas and solutions. • Soft skills are essential for success in any job or business. These skills are necessary for effective teamwork and managing resources effectively. • Encouraging the application of technology can help the community improve their productivity and efficiency.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage the application of simple technology to increase efficiency. • Offering arts and culture classes to nurture talents within the community. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offering arts and culture classes can help individuals in Simpang Village explore and develop their talents.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organizing seminars and workshops to provide an understanding of various career opportunities. • Support for skills development in line with job market needs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seminars and workshops can provide individuals with information about different career paths and opportunities available in the job market. This knowledge can help individuals make informed decisions about their career choices and explore options they may not have been aware of before.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organizing regular forums for farmer groups, home industries and local economic groups. • Help facilitate the exchange of ideas and experiences. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The exchange of ideas and experiences among community members can lead to the sharing of best practices, innovative solutions, and lessons learned, which can benefit the entire community. It can also foster collaboration and networking among different stakeholders, leading to potential partnerships and business opportunities.

Community development initiatives require the involvement of various parties. Therefore, Pasanggrahan Baranangsiang needs to take action to involve stakeholders. This is important for designing how organizations should work together to achieve their goals.

Table 6. Strategy for Collaborating with Stakeholders

Stakeholder	Types	Strategies	Actions
Government	Supportive	Involve	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actively engage in communication with the government to align the organization's programs with their development agenda. • Involve the government in the evaluation and reporting of the organization's activities.
Donors	Supportive	Involve	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uphold transparent communication regarding fund utilization and project impact to maintain donor trust. • Generate financial and progress reports, extend invitations to donors for participation in events or field visits, and engage them in the evaluation process.

Private sector	Mixed Blessing	Collaborate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a project proposal outlining both business and social benefits, emphasizing positive impacts on the company's image, and fostering open dialogue. • Strengthen existing partnerships through mutual benefit evaluation, seeking win-win solutions that meet the needs and expectations of both parties.
Academic Institutions	Supportive	Involve	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involve in strategic planning and assessment of the impact of community development efforts. • Invite students to participate in volunteer activities or internships at the organization.
Organization	Mixed Blessing	Collaborate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborate to collectively enhance community development programs. • Foster transparent communication and dialogue to comprehend the concerns and interests of other organizations. • Seek common ground and identify opportunities for synergy in addressing community challenges collaboratively.
Local Community	Mixed Blessing	Collaborate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage citizens in the planning of programs, offering transparent and accessible information, and establishing a platform for feedback. • Comprehend and address the concerns and expectations of the community, garnering support through active participation and a community-based approach. • Collaborating with community leaders and influential groups to establish connections between the organization and the community.
Members of organization	Supportive	Involve	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance the motivation and engagement of organizational members by actively involving them in decision-making and offering opportunities for personal development. • Open and transparent communication with members within the organization. • Conduct regular meetings to attentively consider member input, arrange training

			and workshops, and acknowledge individual and team accomplishments.
Media and General public	Marginal	Monitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maximize the use of social media platforms for the dissemination of information and updates regarding the organization's activities.
Other Institution	Supportive	Involve	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Include partners in strategic planning, assess the outcomes of collaborative efforts, and regularly express appreciation for their contributions. Enhance partnerships by assessing mutual benefits and actively seeking solutions that are advantageous for both parties, ensuring alignment with the needs and expectations of each other.

Figure 9. Strategy for Collaborating with Stakeholders

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Simpang Village presents a comprehensive opportunity for holistic community development. The various programs proposed aim to address various aspects of economic growth. This includes implementing a technical training program to educate farmers on modern and efficient agricultural techniques, providing assistance and access to advanced farming equipment. An extension program is designed to introduce organic and sustainable farming practices, with technical support for the implementation of environmentally friendly methods. Moreover, there are initiatives for training in processing agricultural products, fostering cooperative development to enhance business competitiveness, and encouraging diversification across various sectors. The goal is to support local businesses in reaching wider markets.

Efforts to increase accessibility and improve the quality of education for the community include opening reading, writing and mathematics classes, additional skills training through non-formal classes, and creativity training programs to increase innovation in local businesses. Soft skills, including leadership, communication, problem solving, and collaboration, will also be emphasized. Training programs will be aligned with the skills required in emerging industrial sectors. Seminars and workshops should be organized to provide insights into various career opportunities, supporting skills development in alignment with job market needs. Regular forums also need to be established for farmer groups, home industries, and local economic groups, for fostering collaboration and collective progress within the community.

Pasanggrahan Baranangsiang needs to take a collaborative approach with the private sector, other organizations and local communities. Then take an involving approach to government, donors, academic institutions, members of organizations and other institutions. Lastly, for the media and general public, the approach that needs to be taken is monitoring.

FURTHER STUDY

For further study, there is a need for research that focuses on explore collaboration models that involve partnerships between the public sector, private sector, and non-profit organizations in the context of community development. This could include studying effective management approaches for fostering collaboration, coordination, and shared decision-making among multiple stakeholders to achieve sustainable development outcomes.

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